

**DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF AN ADVANCED SYSTEM
FOR WIND RESOURCE ASSESSMENT**

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Award of the Degree of Master of Science in Advanced Manufacturing
and Automation Engineering in the School of Engineering of Dedan
Kimathi University of Technology**

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DECLARATION

This thesis is my original work and to my knowledge has not been presented in any University or Institution for a degree, or for consideration of any certification.

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DEDICATION

To my entire family and friends who contributed to making this work a success!

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Foremost, I bless the God and Father of my Lord Jesus Christ, who has blessed me.

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ABSTRACT

The global renewable energy demand has been on the rise since 1870s. A report published by Global Wind Energy Council (GWEC) showed that the global cumulative installed wind capacity rose from 10MW in 1980 to 539.6GW in 2017. In total, Asia, Europe, America, and Pacific regions contributed to 99.16% of the global wind capacity, while Africa and the Middle East took up the remaining 0.84% by the end of 2017. Generally, there is a need for developing countries to invest more in wind energy to significantly contribute to the global wind power installed capacity. Before installing a wind turbine, wind data for a prospected site needs to be collected for a minimum of one year. The analysis is then done and a detailed wind resource assessment report prepared. For developing countries, instruments and expertise for carrying out wind resource assessment are all imported, which is an additional hindrance to wind power investment. Current instruments for collecting wind data are not able to solely collect wind data from numerous masts located far from each other, analyse the collected data without human intervention, and effectively provide the results of interest to the user when needed. Various solutions to this problem have been attempted, but they are isolated in the sense that one specialist handles the instrumentation part of the problem, then another specialist handles the analysis and resource assessment part. An advanced system that acquires wind data from remote locations wirelessly (in real-time), does wind data analysis automatically, and manages results securely and conveniently as demanded by the user, would significantly reduce wind resource assessment hustles and financial burden. This study presents the design and implementation of such a system, aiming at cutting down the cost of wind resource assessment hence facilitating wind power investment, especially in developing countries. This study involved the design of Cup-Vane Anemometer parts, 3D-Printing, installation of the required embedded systems, and assembly of the whole system instrument that made up a wireless sensor node. After this, the instrument was calibrated in the lab. Using Internet of Things (IoT) technology, software algorithms were developed around a distant fog-cloud-connected minicomputer (sink node), to receive data and do all the required data analysis and management according to the user's set demands. This research gave rise to a system that after installation, reliably collected wind data from a site within a mean fitting deviation of $\pm 0.063398m/s$, stored, analysed, and relayed results to the user on request. These results included wind speed, direction distributions, as well as power predictions. This study has been verified in the lab using 1 – 16m/s wind speeds and outside in an open field with 1 – 5m/s wind speeds.

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ABBREVIATIONS

EEPROM	Electrically Erasable Programmable Read-Only Memory
WAsP	Wind Atlas Analysis and Application Program
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
ANSI	American National Standard Institute
PSDF	Power Spectral Density Function
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
GIS	Geographic Information System
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
PDF	Probability Density Function
WRA	Wind Resource Assessment
AEP	Annual Energy Production
WSN	Wireless Sensor Network
CAD	Computer Aided Design
RPM	Revolutions Per Minute
I^2C	Inter-Integrated Circuit
RPi3	Raspberry Pi Version 3
PCB	Printed Circuit Board
IoT	Internet of Things
CCW	Counterclockwise
CW	Clockwise
3DP	3D-Print

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

This chapter lays down the process of wind resource assessment (WRA) and its importance in this study. The challenges involved in this process are identified, which constitute the objectives of this study. The scope of this work and the significance of carrying out this research is also outlined in this chapter.

1.1 Background of the Study

When generating energy from fossil fuels, 70-75% of carbon dioxide emissions are released to the environment. Carbon dioxide (CO_2) is the main greenhouse gas. This increases the impacts of global warming Hoel & Kverndokk (1996). To reduce these effects of global warming, it is prudent for nations to invest in wind energy. Wind energy is one of the cleanest and potentially cheapest source of renewable energy An et al. (2014). Compared to other energy sources that involve burning of fossil fuels, the processes involved in wind energy production does not result to environmental pollution. Even though renewable energy systems are generally costlier than those making use of fossil fuel, it is reported that wind energy cost is rapidly becoming equal to that of fossil fuel sources McCrone et al. (2014).

A wind power development report published by World Bank in 2009 Kooten & Timilsina (2009) showed that, the global wind power generation capacity rose from 10MW in 1980 to 94.12GW in 2007. In total, the installed wind power in developed countries was 85% of the global wind power installation in 2007. Adding China and India into this list made it rise to 98.3% of the global wind power generation capacity.

The rest of the developing countries took up the remaining 1.7%.

Another recent report published by Global Wind Energy Council (GWEC) Fried (2017) showed that, the global cumulative installed wind capacity rose from 23.9GW in 2001 to 539.6GW in 2017. In total, Asia, Europe, America, and Pacific regions contributed to 99.16% of the global wind capacity, while Africa and the Middle East took up the remaining 0.84%; by the end of 2017.

This means that there is a need for developing countries to invest more in wind energy to significantly contribute to the global wind power installed capacity. Before setting up small or large scale wind turbine project, it is important to carry out a WRA around the site where the wind turbine is to be installed. This is vital in determining the feasibility of the wind turbine project, its productivity and if it is worth to invest in. In reference to An et al. (2014); Brower (2012); Brower et al. (2010), there are key steps involved in WRA. These steps are discussed next.

1.1.1 Site Prospecting

Site prospecting/exploration involves identifying a potential site for wind energy farming. Third party information is widely used to identify a potential site. A large bare area is generally checked to see if it is worth further investigation. During this step, other factors such as the economic value of the area and also the accessibility of the site is put into consideration. Checking geographic information system (GIS), information and graphical map representation of the site can greatly help in making the right decision about site identification Brower (2012).

From this site prospecting exercise, a reliable amount of wind speed ranging from $5m/s$ is expected at heights of around $60m$ to $100m$ above the ground. If this is found positive, it may imply that a small or large scale wind turbine can successfully be installed at that site. However, it is recommended that the transmission distance from the site to where this energy is required to be less than $21km$ for around $116KV$. At the end of site exploration exercise, AEP estimation accuracy is about $\pm 50\%$ An et al. (2014).

Apart from wind data and its potential energy, it is important to check the topography of the site to see to it that it will be possible to construct the required structures. Vehicles coming in and vehicles bringing building materials should be able to do so at ease, otherwise, the cost of putting up the necessary roads should be factored in. A land that is free from obstacles such as trees and buildings is preferred. In addition to these considerations, the prospected wind energy project should have local support and should be free from political or cultural barriers Brower et al. (2010). When setting up a wind turbine, a smooth hill is preferred. This is as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Wind Turbine Sites GreenSpec (2014)

In addition to the topography, it is important to consider the obstacles that are found around the prospected site since they introduce turbulence to the wind flow. The position of the wind turbine should be identified in consideration to the position of the obstacles Troen et al. (1989). This is as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Wind Turbine Obstacles GreenSpec (2014)

1.1.2 Measurement Campaign

This stage is aimed at improving the $\pm 50\%$ accuracy as much as possible. This is hence one of the most sensitive stages. In this stage, the actual wind data is collected using monitoring instruments. The accuracy of these instruments must be within the acceptable standards. An inaccuracy of $\pm 5\%$ in wind velocity measurement can result to around $\pm 10\%$ inaccuracy in AEP and revenue prediction An et al. (2014).

The collected wind data is stored safely in a way that it can be accessed when it is needed for analysis. The main goal of this step is to have reliable data collected by calibrated instruments. To begin with, instruments for collecting and logging this wind data, say wind velocity, must be identified. There are various instruments that can be used to measure the wind velocity. In reference to Dines & Henry (n.d.); Middleton (1969); Middleton & Spilhaus (1953), these instruments may include the following:

1. Velocity Anemometers

- i) Cup anemometer
- ii) Windmill anemometer
- iii) Hot-wire anemometer
- iv) Laser doppler anemometers
- v) Sodar and Lidar anemometers
- vi) Ping-pong ball anemometers

2. Pressure Anemometers

- i) Plate anemometers
- ii) Tube anemometers

Despite the recent growth of sodar and ladar anemometers, from the above listed instruments, the cup anemometer is the most suitable and widely accepted as the standard instrument for measuring wind speed Gasch & Twele (2012); Hunter (2003); IEC (2005); Pindado et al. (2014). Among other attractive advantages, in his research article, L. Kristensen states that; 'experience has shown that the cup anemometer is a robust and reliable instrument which can operate unattended for years' Kristensen (1999). To set up the required instruments for wind data collection as shown in Figure

3, a tower of around 60 – 100m high is required. A dedicated tower can be constructed or a pre-existing tower can be used. A dedicated tower is recommended since a number of scientific factors are considered before the tower is put in place Brower (2012).

When constructing a dedicated tower, it is required that it be installed with lightning arrester. This tower should be placed as far as possible; away from any obstructions. The location of this tower should be a representation of where the turbine will be constructed Ammonit (2012). However, for large wind turbine projects, a number of these towers should be constructed to capture the full range of environmental conditions Brower et al. (2010). In reference to WRA guidelines Brower (2012), the instrumentation tower should have at least three levels of around 10m separation distance from the top.

Figure 3: Wind Data Measurement and Logging RTPL (2014)

Wide separation distance helps to minimise the wind shear uncertainty. A top to bottom anemometer height ratio of about 1.6 is recommended Brower et al. (2010). Two cup anemometers should be installed at each of the three levels. At least one wind vane should be installed in two of the levels. It is recommended that this wind data be collected for at least one year. This helps to capture seasonal variations in the collected wind data. In connection to this, it is vital to install other important instruments for this one year of data collection. These instruments include temperature sensors, pressure sensors, and solar intensity sensors. An appropriate power supply and data logger is also selected at this stage. The data logger must be well capable of securely storing data from all the installed sensors, in an appropriate format (.csv, .txt) and should be well accessible when it is needed.

1.1.3 Data Analysis

In this stage, the data collected is first transferred into a computing environment and screened for possible obvious errors Hoel & Kverndokk (1996). The accumulated monthly, quarterly or yearly data is usually taken through a validation process which basically detects and flags out invalid data. In wind data validation process, the techniques used are focused to minimise the statistical false-positive and false-negative errors. In the case where some data is flagged invalid during the validation process, the data from the other parallel instrument in the same level is used Brower et al. (2010). To notice the invalid data, the collected data is compared with certain allowable limits as seen in Table 1.

Table 1: Wind data: Allowable upper and lower limits Brower et al. (2010)

Sample Parameter*	Validation Criteria
Wind Speed: Horizontal	
Average	Offset < Avg. < 30m/s
Standard Deviation	0 < Std. Dev. < 3m/s
Maximum Gust	Offset < Max < 35m/s
Wind Direction	
Average	0 < Avg. < 360°
Standard Deviation	3° < Std. Dev. < 75°
Temperature	
Typical Range	-35° < Avg. < 35°C
Solar Radiation	
Typical Range	Offset < Avg. < 1200W/m ²
Wind Speed: Vertical	
Average **(S/C)	Offset < Avg. < ±(2/4)m/s
Standard Deviation	Offset < Std. Dev. < ±(1/2)m/s
Maximum Gust	Offset < Max < ±(3/6)m/s
Barometric Pressure	
Average	Optional: Sea Level Shown 94kPa < Avg. < 106kPa
Differential Temperature	
Average Difference	Optional > 1.0°C (daytime)
Average Difference	< 1.0°C (overnight)
* All monitoring levels except where noted	
** (S/C): Simple/Complex Terrain	

1.1.4 Data Reporting

To characterise the collected wind data, there are different reports expected at the end of a wind resource assessment exercise. First, time series observations are presented. This observation presents wind speed at different height of the mast versus time. These are real observations from the prospected site. It is expected that wind speeds at lower heights will be lower than the wind speeds at higher heights Troen et al. (1989). The differences in wind speed changes during the night and during the day

can be observed using this presentation.

The next step is to put data into a distribution, usually, a Weibull distribution which is an approximate fit to the data distribution. This is important in showing the wind speed frequency and the most likely instantaneous wind speed. In addition, this distribution makes further calculations easier, lighter and less time consuming to the computer; instead of using every single set of collected data Manwell et al. (2009).

At this point, wind energy that can be extracted from the point of data collection can be calculated and plotted. To come up with a wind map of the prospected site, compensation for the site roughness and topography are performed. This takes into consideration the buildings, trees, hills, valleys and other obstacles Mortensen (2015). After this, wind climate of the prospected site is predicted. This gives a broad picture about the best points where wind turbines can be installed. This is as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Wind Energy Prediction Mortensen (2015)

1.2 Problem Statement

From the global wind energy investment statistics, it is clear that developing countries need to invest more in wind energy. The practice of installing a wind turbine is that wind data for the prospected site must be collected for at least one year. The wind data analysis is then done, followed by a comprehensive wind resource assessment report. This is as discussed in the background of this study. The exercise requires calibrated instruments, software licenses, and specialists. To most developing countries, all these requirements are expensively imported. This contributes to the difficulties of rapid wind energy investment and may sometimes frustrate the whole project.

Current instruments for collecting wind data are not able to solely collect wind data from numerous decentralised masts, analyse the collected data without human intervention, and at the same time provide the results of interest to the user when needed; in an effective and secure way. Various solutions for this problem have been attempted, but they are isolated. One expert may specialise in instrumentation, while another specialises in analysis and wind resource assessment. This introduces a lot of middle parties before wind resource assessment exercise is completed.

1.3 Goal of the Research

The utmost goal of this study was to put together the intricate elements of Wind Resource Assessment into a cost-effective system.

1.3.1 Main Objective

The main objective of this study was to develop a cost-effective system for performing Wind Resource Assessment automatically, starting from data acquisition to energy prediction.

1.3.2 Specific Objectives

The specific objectives of this study were to:

- (i) Design the wireless Cup-Vane Anemometer subsystems
- (ii) 3D-Print and assemble the wireless Cup-Vane Anemometer parts
- (iii) Calibrate the wireless 3D-Printed Cup-Vane Anemometer
- (iv) Implement an Internet of Things system for auto data analysis and management
- (v) Test the wireless 3D-Printed Cup-Vane Anemometer in an open field

1.4 Significance of the Study

As discussed in the background of this study, there are various processes, instruments, and professional parties involved in successful wind resource assessment. Many small scale farmers, particularly in the developing countries, are intimidated by WRA complexity. Considering this difficulty, a complete system like the one presented in this study is an indispensable cost effective tool to such groups, for predicting wind power resource in specific remote sites, hence facilitating wind energy investment projects.

1.5 Scope of the Study

This study begins with the design of instruments involved in wind data acquisition; the cup anemometer and the wind vane. The designed parts are 3D-Printed. All the sensors required for wind speed, wind direction, pressure, altitude, temperature, and humidity are installed and the parts assembled together to make a cup-vane anemometer as one instrument. From here, the embedded system for data logging is designed and implemented.

The embedded system is then programmed to understand the signals from sensors, save, and transmit wind data to a distant central minicomputer. The instrument is then calibrated. This study ends with algorithm development for the minicomputer to receive the data, save, perform the required processing and upload the backup data and reports to the internet for presentation or further processing.

1.6 Thesis Outline

This thesis consists of five main chapters:

Chapter ONE introduces this study and the issues that necessitated it. The problem statement is formulated and the objectives of this study identified. The significance and scope of this study is also outlined in this chapter.

Chapter TWO presents the current studies that has been carried out in relation to this research. The remarks pertaining to the research that has already been done are also discussed in this chapter.

Chapter THREE consists the details of the methods and the techniques used to solve the problems identified by this research.

Chapter FOUR presents all the results, analysis and discussions pertaining to the data collected during the laboratory and field exercises.

Chapter FIVE gives a summary of the major findings of this research. This chapter also provides recommendations about the possible future studies.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter describes the current knowledge and contributions that has been done in regard to novelty of this study.

2.1 Cup and Vane Anemometer Design

Taking a look at the design of cup anemometer, since its invention by T. R. Robinson in 1846, the greatest interest in the cup anemometer design was only its linearity. Even though further studies has shown that it is actually 'almost linear' Kristensen (1999), the calibration of the cup anemometer is highly linear. This is still an attractive feature that makes calibration process easy and reliable. However, from the year 1920, this linearity feature of interest has shifted to the *over-speeding* nature of the cup anemometer.

As explained by L. Kristensen *et al.*, over-speeding of cup anemometers is a characteristic effect caused by the fact that cup anemometers tend to respond more to an increase in speed than to breaking Kristensen (1999). This is commonly known as the *asymmetric response* of the cup anemometers. This presents a non-linear response to wind speed changes. This is perceived to be a negative feature but it is actually a property that gets the cup anemometer to start off Kristensen (1999); Kristensen et al. (2014).

For wind vane design, J. Wieringa showed wind vane motion described by damping ratio, natural wavelength and decay distance to be insufficiently described by a second order equation as a result of the torque changes with a change in the angle of attack Wieringa (1967). With measured vane dimensions, a relationship was derived between the measured vane dimensions and motion constants. It was shown that with a fin attached to the vane, the motion of the vane is independent of the fin area. A closer look at the modern vane designs reveals that most anemometer developers are adopting the cup-vane design to save on materials, weight, as well as space.

In a bid to improve the responsiveness of wind vane direction measurements, Johann *et al.* developed a mathematical model describing the dynamic behaviour of a wind vane Laurent et al. (2016). This model was then used to determine the best form factor that will have the best response to the disturbances that the vane will encounter. The team also took into account the model dynamic characteristics by using a predictive filter on a digital signal processing.

2.2 3D-Printing

3D Printing is currently the fastest way of manufacturing few units of a complex-shaped 3-dimensional product. 3D printing starts by preparing a 3D model using a mechanical computer aided design software or by 3D scanning the pre-existing model using a 3D scanner. The prepared 3D digital model in the computer is then sliced by a software into a G-Code that describes each 2D layer that makes up the 3D model. The 3D Printer is then able to make a physical 3-dimensional product, born in the analogue world Kamran & Saxena (2016).

In the paper 'The Impact and Application of 3D-Printing Technology' Mpofu et al. (2014), a comprehensive study explained how 3D printing has been embraced by every sector involved in manufacturing. The largest 3D printing applications going to making functional models, spare parts, research and artistic items. As recorded, 3D printing lowers cost of manufacturing, improves efficiency and brings about high flexibility Mpofu et al. (2014). It has been predicted that 3D printed parts market will grow to an 8.4 billion dollar industry by 2025 Thryft (2014).

In the 2016 Global Congress on Manufacturing and Management, Phani *et al.* explained how natural, build and digital environments are shaping the economies and societies through smart living. Mass customisation of products and services is getting preferred over mass production Paritalaa et al. (2017). 3D printing as a 'tool-less' digital manufacturing technique, strives to make products with exact specifications as required. The current global diversification and existence of unpredictable market trends is pushing manufacturing to its limits. As explained Paritalaa et al. (2017), unlike the traditional manufacturing technologies, digital manufacturing is a promising technology that fit to the current dynamic market trends.

At an advanced level, 3D Printing technology is being used to print electronic devices as well as their casing. Yuanyuan *et al.* Xu et al. (2017) in their review paper 'The Boom in 3D-Printed Sensor Technology', showed a significant growth and advancement in 3D Printing technology for the manufacturing of sensors. A good example is force sensors used in various systems. Commercial force sensors are not exactly fitted to the specific system requirements and end up being over-size, more expensive or not performing exactly as required.

3D Printing comes in handy to make the exact force sensor with the exact specifications. To 3D-Print electronics, a CAD file is prepared as usual, then different conductive inks are used to put together the electronic parts layer by layer Xu et al. (2017). For small batches, 3D Printing has introduced fabrication freedom. This trend is expected to improve in future.

2.3 Internet of Things (IoT) Technology

The Internet of Things depends on devices that collect the physical data and deliver it to the internet. The data collected by the IoT devices is enormous. In fact, the 'IoT is a prototypical example of big data' Cecchinel et al. (2015). Big data collection supports the possibility of innovation and offers possible solutions through creation of information. One limitation in collection of this data is that there is no comprehensive approach about how this data should be collected Cecchinel et al. (2015). In their article, Cyril *et al.* provided an architectural solution to the handling of the IoT data. In this case, the IoT architects handle sensors and stores the large amounts of data produced by the IoT sensors in order to tackle the data storage challenges. A supportive architecture is developed that supports the sensors from data collection to management. It also gives room for users who wants to use the big data for research.

Connecting IoT devices direct to the cloud systems introduces another set of challenges. These challenges include power consumption, network failure and security issues. Hany *et al.* puts more emphasis on fog computing instead of cloud computing Atlam et al. (2018). This brings the cloud services closer to the devices as the computation is done at the IoT device.

Fog computing allows faster responses, reliability and efficiency. Sending all the regular sensor data to the cloud requires huge amounts of bandwidth Y. et al. (2017). Fog computing also provides data processing and storage just like cloud computing. This reduces network traffic, latency, and introduces important features such as distributed computing and storage resources Z. et al. (2017). This fog computing feature was thus adopted in this research.

In IoT data handling, data is first acquired from a physical environment by the sensors. Through a wireless sensor network, all these data are collected from the physical world into a cyber world. With the increasing IoT big data, bandwidth and energy requirements rise drastically. It has become very expensive and unnecessary to collect every single exact data from the sensors. Siyao *et al.* discussed solutions to this problem that involve development of prediction algorithms that only receive exact data from the sensors, only if this data cannot be predicted Cheng et al. (2017). Their study also reviewed approximate data collection algorithms that may come in handy when addressing this big data collection issue.

Internet of Things work together with the wireless sensor networks (WSN). The IoT sensors send data to the central processing node (sink node) with the help of WSN. The WSN introduces such problems as coverage, power optimisation, efficiency and security. Applications are needed to manage the WSN into making the best and optimal decisions that minimise these challenges. In connection to this, IoT sensors in the WSN need to be able to make decisions in addition to transmitting data Luong et al. (2016).

Along with using the traditional optimisation methods to assist in sensor decision making, Nguyen *et al.* introduced the aspect of economic pricing models to determine optimal interactions between the interested parties in the IoT world Luong et al. (2016). This addresses the data collection, communication and data exchange issues through incentives.

2.4 Low-cost Data Acquisition Systems

Sandro C.S. Juca *et al.*, recognised that for the developing countries, data acquisition systems are fully an imported technology which poses financial and other barriers in to the renewable energy investment Jucá et al. (2011). In their solution, a USB interface was preferred as opposed to the earlier versions which used TTL/RS-232 interfaces for transmission. For data storage, it was found that the previous solutions used hard disks which required constant maintenance. A data acquisition EEPROM was hence used and a possibility of using GPS/GPRS for data transmission was explained. A microcontroller was used to manage all the I^2C chips.

Manish Kumar and Thanachai, worked on a remote data acquisition system specifically applied to wind data acquisition. The acquired data was saved to a hard disk, displayed by the monitor and transmitted to the internet via TCP/IP protocol Das & Leephakpreeda (2012). The transmission into a website was done with the help of RS-232 communication and a GSM modem. Each station sent data similarly. An LCD display was attached to the microcontroller (at the site) to display instantaneous measurements. The remote data acquisition for wind measurement had a network cable that connected the data acquisition system to the computer server.

A similar work to that of Manish Kumar published by Yahya S. H. Khraisat addressed the particular issue of automating data collection from remote location and delivering it to a meteorological station instead of using a telephone method that only existed then in Jordan Khraisat (2012).

Amar Adane *et al.*, in their paper about design of a microcontroller based data acquisition system, a meteorological data acquisition system was presented Adane et al. (2014). This system was cost effective and was able to automatically get sensors data from the station. The acquired data was then transferred to a computer through a serial connection. The computer then analysed the data and relayed the required reports.

A case in point for large scale wind farms was discussed by Neha and Kumar Chauhan & Kumar (2014). A wireless SCADA system that did monitoring and collected the required data parameters remotely was used. A mobile network based on GPRS was utilised when sending data packets from the remote location. This industrial system saved time and money since there was no need to send a specialist in every location to collect data or perform minor adjustments.

Eftichiof and Kostas Koutroulis & Kalaitzakis (2002) had described a similar system but more cost effective in the sense that, it was based on a simple microcontroller. This microcontroller was interfaced with sensors to collect data and deliver it to the computer via RS-232 connection. This data was then further processed by the LabView program.

Chin and Tan Nguyen et al. (2015) discussed a WSN method, which was very inspiring to this study. A star node network of six sensors based on XBee was used to collect data from different (remote) locations. The data was then sent to a data logger through a gateway from each node. This data was then processed and uploaded to the internet via GSM network for further processing. Nisha and Versha Gahlot et al. (2015) discussed a notably similar method, built around a cost effective microcontroller.

A recent article (2017) published by SriLakshmi *et al.* SriLakshmi et al. (2017), discussed a wireless method of data collection using an ESP8266 module, which was then, probably the cheapest wireless data collection stand-alone module using the IEEE 802.11 protocol. A microcontroller was interfaced with sensors that measured wind speed, direction and humidity. This data was sent wirelessly from up to a distance of 30m. A computer interface was able to display the sensors parameters as well as provide an online display through a web server. This particular method was however not sufficient for wind resource assessment, given that wind data measurement mast can go up to 100m.

2.5 Wind Resource Assessment Methods

For analysis involved in WRA, a report (2017) by Niels G. Mortensen presented a comprehensive introduction about professional WRA using the WAsP software Mortensen (2017). As discussed, WAsP analysis transforms the observed meteorological data to a regional wind climate. WAsP application transforms this wind climate to the predicted wind climate. This is basically an implementation of *wind atlas methodology* Troen et al. (1989). WAsP also delivers potential annual energy

production reports as well as uncertainty reports.

Rui *et al.* Pereira *et al.* (2010), in their comparative study between WAsP and CFD presented some interesting findings. Having carried out seven test cases, the deviations found in CFD were lower than the deviations found in WAsP, by at least a half in all the test cases. This did not establish that CFD was a better solution than WAsP for WRA. But it provided confidence that other methods such the one developed in this study, stands a chance to perform comprehensive WRA to a certain degree of accuracy.

2.6 Remarks

As reviewed, the research conducted by Kristein *et al.* showed the most critical factors of consideration when designing a cup anemometer Kristensen (1999) . These considerations were followed during the design of the cup anemometer used in this study. In addition, the studies of J. Wieringa, Johann *et al.* Laurent *et al.* (2016); Wieringa (1967), inspired the design and the development of the cup-vane anemometer used in this study.

The data acquisition solution discussed by Sandro C.S. Juca *et al.* was cost effective but did not offer detailed data analysis and management capabilities as applied to WRA Jucá *et al.* (2011). Still, data acquisition in the EEPROM is limited and would still require further retrieving for analysis purposes. In addition, considering the complexity of WRA data acquisition, a USB cable can only be so long.

The idea offered by Manish Kumar and Thanachai in their publication almost closed the gap Das & Leephakpreeda (2012). However, considering collection of wind data

from different remote masts, this method was not sufficiently decentralised. Still, it did not provide a report about WRA in the prospected site.

Data acquisition was still based on third party cup anemometer Das & Leephakpreeda (2012), which means that a small scale wind farmer in a developing country would have to rely on such company to supply the instrument. Sending each set of data to the internet (instead of final result) increases payment charges to the internet data provider.

Reviewing the work of Amar Adane *et al.* as discussed earlier, reveals that even though this article did not address the wind data acquisition, analysis and management problem, the cost effective microcontroller solution offered in this study was inspiring Adane et al. (2014). However, this solution was not decentralised and required the use of cables to transmit data to the computer for analysis.

As has been the practice, WRA is performed by disintegrated systems. Different parties are usually involved, from data acquisition to WRA reporting. The clients are comfortable with this, since there are funds allocated for that project, and the core business is to have a comprehensive WRA report. The need to compress and leave part of WRA process (data acquisition, analysis and management) to a single cost effective instrument system has not been a priority. However, as discussed in the literature review, different parties have made considerable efforts to get a solution for this query but not with the complete goal of wind resource assessment that this study seeks to address.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

In an attempt to close the gaps discussed in literature review, this chapter describes in detail how the solution offered in this study was implemented.

3.1 Advanced Wind Resource Assessment System

Design

In a nutshell, the cup anemometer and wind vane parts were designed in Autodesk Inventor and 3D-Printed using Makerbot 3D-Printer. The required sensors and embedded systems were installed to make a cup-vane anemometer. This instrument was calibrated in Dedan Kimathi University laboratory, in line with the published standards IEC (2005). This instrument (wireless cup-vane anemometer) transmitted data via an XBee WSN. This gave room for decentralised remote data transmission. It was able to store raw data into an SD card as well as send data to a central minicomputer. The minicomputer did the required analysis and uploaded the reports and backup data online. This made it possible to access results as was, or request for custom analysis and reports. This system was powered by 5V solar power-bank.

The steps involved in WRA process can be summarised into four main stages; site prospecting, wind measurement, AEP model based estimation, and loss-uncertainty estimation. Site prospects are usually available on the external third party sources which have performed preliminary WRA based on numerical weather prediction. In connection to this, the system implementation focused on the last three main steps involved in WRA, which are key in improving the accuracy of AEP estimation. The

system designed in this study is represented by the diagram shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Advanced WRA System

This chapter illustrates in detail, how the system design shown in Figure 1 was achieved.

3.2 Design of the Cup-Vane Anemometer

The high demand in the accuracy of the cup anemometer when measuring wind speed has necessitated various studies on the cup anemometer dynamics; to ensure that it can provide reliable results for a long time after it has been calibrated. Following the cup anemometer dynamics research, it has now been proven that the calibration of the cup anemometer depends only on its *rotor geometry* Kristensen (1999); Kristensen et al. (2014); Pindado et al. (2014); Roibas-Millan et al. (2017). Calibration of the cup anemometer does not depend on its rotor mass as might be perceived. For this reason, the main concern in the design of the following cup anemometer was its geometry

It is desirable that the cups of the cup-vane anemometer be conical, designed to maximise on the drag force. Light cup anemometers are least prone to overspeeding problem, and are more sensitive to the moving wind Kristensen (1999). This formed the basis for the second criteria for designing cups for the cup-vane anemometer. The design criteria for the vane of the cup-vane anemometer was to make the tail blade light and shaped to respond to wind speeds from approximately $1m/s$ to reduce the

feathery flipping effect. The material used during 3D printing was PolyLactic Acid (PLA). PLA is suitable for quick prototyping and testing as was required here. For a long term implementation, the material would have to be changed to Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS) or carbon fibre to improve on durability.

With these considerations at hand and inspiration from the studies of Johann and Thies Anemometer S11100 design Climatik (2012); Laurent et al. (2016), the cup-vane anemometer used in this study was designed with the help of Autodesk Inventor software. This is shown in the Figure 2.

The design of the Figure 2 captured the main parts of the cup-vane anemometer. However, a body had to be designed to hold together the cup-vane design, as well as the temperature, humidity, pressure and altitude sensors. The cup-vane body was hence designed in consideration with the sensors and the supportive embedded systems that were to be installed.

Figure 2: Cup-Vane Anemometer Design

The design presented in Figure 3 shows the virtual assembly of the complete cup-vane anemometer. The part numbers in Figure 3 are described in parts Table 1.

Figure 3: Cup-Vane Virtual Assembly

Table 1: Cup-Vane Assembly: Parts List

PARTS LIST			
ITEM	QTY	PART NO.	DESCRIPTION
1	1	CVA-01	Anemometer cup holder
2	3	CVA-02	Anemometer cup
3	1	CVA-03	Rotor coupling
4	1	CVA-04	RPM sensor
5	1	CVA-05	T-joint
6	2	CVA-06	RPM sensor cover
7	1	CVA-07	Temp-Hum cover
8	1	CVA-08	Upper shell
9	1	CVA-09	Bearing
10	1	CVA-10	Vane base
11	1	CVA-11	Blade base
12	1	CVA-12	Vane tip
13	1	CVA-13	Tail blade

3.3 Wireless Sensor Node Design

3.3.1 Embedded Systems Design

The focus of this design was to come up with a wireless data logger in a small form factor as opposed to the industrial PLC and SCADA systems. The design criteria for this system was to keep its cost relatively low in a way that it can all be done

in the lab. Still, the wireless data logger needed to be able to operate on available power-banks. In comparison to the other available options such as ARM, PIC and TI microcontrollers, Atmel family was found to be the most simple and cost effective with similar performance. The wireless data logger used in this study was built around the Atmega328P-AU microcontroller. This implementation also had an XBee radio capable of transmitting data via Zigbee IEEE 802.15.4 protocol, to a central station located up to 100m away. A simplified representation of the schematic used is as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Data Logger Schematic

The final implementation was in form of a compact PCB enclosed in a 3D-Printed case. This is as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Complete Embedded System

The implementation represented in Figure 4 was flashed with a program that captured and transmitted data effectively from all the installed sensors. This program is the algorithm summarised in the next subsection.

3.3.2 Wireless Sensor Node Algorithm

In this case, the main task for this algorithm was pre-processing – to prepare the station's embedded systems to collect the data from sensors and send that data to the main post-processing station located far from it. This algorithm was prepared in an ANSI C/C++ development environment. To start with, the sensors pins and addresses were defined as illustrated next.

```
#define DHTTYPE DHT11  
  
#define DHTPIN 4  
  
#define hmcAddr 0x1E  
  
#define bmpAddr 0x77  
  
#define encPinA 2  
  
#define encPinB 3
```

Some of the sensors used needed communicate via I^2C protocol. Their addresses were defined and the required sensor libraries were included into the program:

```
#include <Adafruit_HMC5883_U.h>  
  
#include <Adafruit_BMP085.h>  
  
#include <Wire.h>  
  
#include <DHT.h>
```

The necessary setups were prepared inside a function that was only called once. This preparation included specification of the involved sensor interrupt, pulling up the internal resistors and starting up the sensors as well as the serial communication:

```
void setup()
{
    attachInterrupt(0, doEncoder, RISING);

    pinMode(encPinA, INPUT);

    pinMode(encPinB, INPUT);

    digitalWrite(encPinA, HIGH);

    digitalWrite(encPinB, HIGH);

    Serial.begin(38400);

    Wire.begin();

    dht.begin();

    bmp.begin();

    mag.begin();
}
```

The iteration required was done in one loop function. During the entire iteration, time elapsing was noted by the program. Sensors were configured to deliver the data to the serial as soon as they acquired it. The sensors calibration details were to be considered in this iteration as well. In this section, the speed sensor was prepared to always provide the current revolutions per minute:

```
void loop()
{
    time_now = millis();
```

```

newEncPos = encPos;

newtym = millis();

rpm = (newEncPos-oldEncPos) * 1000 /(newtym-oldtym);

    if(rpm >= 0 || rpm <= 0)
    {

        Serial.print (rpm);

        Serial.print(",");

    }

oldEncPos = newEncPos;

oldtym = newtym;

```

The compass sensor was configured to capture the direction of the wind vane tail and deliver the data to the serial. Declination angle is taken care of:

```

Wire.beginTransmission(hmcAddr);

sensors_event_t event;

mag.getEvent(&event);

event.magnetic.x;

event.magnetic.y;

event.magnetic.z;

Wire.endTransmission();

```

```

float heading = atan2(event.magnetic.y, event.magnetic.x);

float declinationAngle = 0.22;

heading += declinationAngle;

if(heading < 0)

    heading += 2*PI;

if(heading > 2*PI)

    heading -= 2*PI;

float headingDegrees = heading * 180/M_PI;

Serial.print(headingDegrees);

Serial.print(",");

```

A request to the sensor responsible for reading the temperature, pressure and altitude was made to transmit data and deliver it to the serial in a comma separated format. A similar request was made for the rest of the sensors:

```

Wire.beginTransmission(bmpAddr);

Serial.print(bmp.readTemperature());

Serial.print(",");

Serial.print(bmp.readPressure());

Serial.print(",");

Serial.print(bmp.readAltitude());

Serial.print(",");

Wire.endTransmission();

```

At this point, all the subsystems design required for the wireless 3D-Printed Cup-Vane Anemometer were complete. The next step was to do the actual 3D-Printing, assemble the printed parts as well as install the sensors.

3.4 3D-Printing and Assembly

After design, all the parts were converted to .stl file format ready for printing. 3D-Printing was done using MakerBot 3D-Printer. The parameters used for printing the designed parts were set as shown in the Figure 6.

(a) Device Settings

(b) Infill Settings

Figure 6: 3D-Printing Parameter Setting

The individual parts were printed separately, one at a time, waiting to be assembled.

The physical setup for the 3D-Printing exercise was as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: 3D-Printing Setup

After printing all the cup-vane anemometer parts, all the internal sensors were installed as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Sensor Installation

Other sensors such as temperature and altitude sensors were installed in a similar way. This installation exercise included all the wiring needed for every sensor to get power and deliver the data signals.

The complete installation of the sensors into the cup-vane body was as shown in Figure 9 (a). From this point, the anemometer cups and the wind vane tail blade were installed. The whole assembly was then painted and polished to make a finished cup-vane anemometer shown in Figure 9 (b).

Figure 9: Finished Cup-Vane Anemometer

For this cup-vane anemometer to work, it required that an embedded system be designed to capture the sensors signals, translate into the required data and transmit this data to a central minicomputer.

3.5 Calibration Experimental Setup

3.5.1 Preliminary Experimental Setup

The wind tunnel shown in Figure 10 (a) was used to perform the calibration. As seen in the datasheet Armfield (2011), this wind tunnel is not specifically designed for cup-vane anemometer calibration.

However, with close examination of the wind behaviour at its 'test section' and at its 'outlet', the wind produced was used to calibrate the 3D-Printed cup-vane anemometer.

Wind data was collected at point 1 to 4 as shown in the Figure 10 (b). The characteristics of the wind at these points were examined to ensure that the wind speed of the wind coming out at point 4 was well known. This analysis was essential in improving the calibration accuracy.

Figure 10: Armfield Wind Tunnel Setup

For accuracy and comparison purposes, there were two wind measuring instruments used in this exercise; a professional digital hand-held manual anemometer Benetech (2015) and the Armfield C15 Armfield (2011) inbuilt differential pressure transducer. The fan in this wind tunnel was controlled by the PC Armfield software which is designed to drive the fan from 0% rotation speed to 100%.

During data collection in this exercise, the fan speed was increased by 3% one step at a time, starting from 13% (when the inbuilt sensor started recording values above 0m/s) to 100%. During this time, the inbuilt sensor was set to collect wind speed data automatically after every 5sec. At the same time, wind speed data was collected manually using the manual anemometer after every 5sec. This 5sec interval allows the sensor to stabilise if it sensed some change Armfield (2011). The fan speed, say 16%, was held constant until the inbuilt (auto) and manual instruments recorded 7 sets of data simultaneously. After the 35sec, the fan rotation speed was increased to the next level and the process repeated till 100% fan speed — one *run* (which took at least $5 \times 7 \times 30 = 1050\text{sec} = 17.5\text{min}$). The screenshot of Table 2 shows the method by which the data was collected for every run (point 2 data sample). During the whole data collection exercise, every run was repeated 2 to 4 times for better accuracy.

Table 2: Wind Tunnel Data Collection

sample_no	time_elapsed_sec	fan_vel	auto_air_vel_ms	man_air_vel_ms	fan_vel	av_auto_air_vel_ms	av_man_air_vel_ms
1	5	13	1.631109314	2.7	13.0000	1.6311	2.7000
2	10	13	1.631109314	2.7			
3	15	13	1.631109314	2.7			
4	20	13	1.631109314	2.7			
5	25	13	1.631109314	2.7			
6	30	13	1.631109314	2.7			
7	35	13	1.631109314	2.7			
8	40	16	2.135623399	3.4	16.0000	2.2517	3.3714
9	45	16	2.135623399	3.3			
10	50	16	2.541900276	3.4			
11	55	16	2.541900276	3.4			
12	60	16	2.135623399	3.4			
13	65	16	2.135623399	3.3			
14	70	16	2.135623399	3.4			
.
.
.
197	985	97	13.94983363	19.2	97.0000	14.0748	19.3000
198	990	97	14.28634687	19.4			
199	995	97	14.08540371	19.4			
200	1000	97	14.15270177	19.3			
201	1005	97	13.74397137	19.2			
202	1010	97	14.15270177	19.4			
203	1015	97	14.15270177	19.2			
204	1020	100	14.61511393	20	100.0000	14.5683	19.9714
205	1025	100	14.61511393	20			
206	1030	100	14.67998382	19.9			
207	1035	100	14.48450261	20			
208	1040	100	14.67998382	19.9			
209	1045	100	14.48450261	20			
210	1050	100	14.41875328	20			

As seen in Table 2, these 7 sets of small variations in the data collected for each fan speed were averaged. Averaging helped to summarise the small variations into a more reliable single value. This method was applied when collecting data at all the points of interest. During this entire process, the guidelines Freitag et al. (June 2001); IEC (2005); Measnet (October 2009) were utilised.

3.5.2 Cup Calibration Setup

The cup anemometer used in this study was build around the Omron incremental rotary encoder. Its datasheet Omron (2015) was intensively used during the construction of the cup anemometer. The setup for cup anemometer calibration exercise was as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Anemometer Calibration Setup

3.5.3 Vane Calibration Setup

Before the vane compass sensor was put to work, it needed to be calibrated. The setup that was used for this exercise is as shown in the Figure 12.

Figure 12: HMC5883L Calibration Setup

This sensor uses I^2C communication protocol. Python running on a RPi3 was used in this calibration exercise. Connection was done as shown in Table 3 and the setup was done as shown in Figure 12.

Table 3: I^2C Connection

HMC5883L	RPi3
<i>SCL</i>	<i>SCL</i>
<i>SDA</i>	<i>SDA</i>
<i>VCC</i>	3V3
<i>GND</i>	<i>GND</i>

As seen in the Figure 12, the sensor was mounted on a 360 degree slip ring connector to make it possible for it to rotate freely through 360 degree. In reference to the sensor datasheet Honeywell (March 2011) and other sources such as Bitify (Nov 17 2013); Instructables (July 14 2015), a program was used for further sensor setup. This as seen in Appendix I.

3.6 IoT Sink Node Algorithm

In this study, looking at Figure 1, the WRA system design required that the transmitted data from the station be received, ready for the analysis. To start with, the required libraries for post-processing were imported:

```
from matplotlib.backends.backend_pdf import PdfPages
import serial, time, datetime
from datetime import date
from timeit import default_timer as timer
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import numpy as np
import scipy.stats as stats
import csv
import smtplib
```

```

from email.MIMEMultipart import MIMEMultipart

from email.MIMEText import MIMEText

from email.MIMEBase import MIMEBase

from email import encoders

import urllib

```

The time within which the subscriber wants the results was specified as follows.

```
hr_sec = 3600/4
```

The program was then prepared to receive data from the station via the minicomputer port. The file names for the documents to be output were prepared at this stage:

```

start = round(timer(),4)

port = '/dev/ttyUSB0'

a = serial.Serial(port,9600)

t_date = datetime.datetime.now()

f_path = '/media/usb/research/wind/logs/'

filename = 'Wind_Data_{}.csv'.format(time.strftime('%d-%m-% ... '))

plt_fig = 'Data_Plot_{}.pdf'.format(time.strftime('%d-%m-%Y_ ... '))

msbjct = 'WIND_DATA_&_ANALYSIS_{}'.format(time.strftime('%d- ... '))

```

As illustrated next, the file into which data was going to be logged was opened and the field names written in the first row. Here, all the data from the station's installed sensors was acquired. The security was also specified at this stage.

```

fil = open(filename, 'ab')

fields = ('t_sec', 'vel_ms', 'dir_deg', 'b_temp_c', 'b_temp_f', ... )

security = 'xxxx'

```

```

wr = csv.DictWriter(fil,fieldnames=fields,lineterminator='\n')
wr.writeheader()
fil.close()

```

At this stage, the subscribers communication details were harnessed. The message that the system shall communicate to the subscriber was also prepared:

```

fromaddr = "xxx@xxx.xxx"
toaddr = ['xxx@xxx.xxx', 'xxx@xxx.xxx']
msg = MIMEMultipart()
msg['From'] = fromaddr
msg['To'] = ','.join(toaddr)
msg['Subject'] = msbjct
body = "Hello,\n\nAttached is the Wind Data and Analysis ..."

```

This is the point where the data entered into the central station, checked, cleaned and was converted into the required format for saving. The system kept track of time all through:

```

while True:
    strg = a.readline()
    cnos = strg.count(',')
    if cnos == 11:
        lst = [float(x) for x in strg.split(',')]
        t_time = [time.strftime('%H:%M:%S')]
        t_elap = [round((timer()-start),4)]
        whl = t_elap+lst

```

```

print whl,

with open(filename, 'ab') as myfile:

    wr = csv.writer(myfile)

    wr.writerow(whl)

    fil.close()

elapsed_time = round(timer(),4)-start

print ' '

```

When it was about time to deliver the requested results by the subscriber, the system loaded the needed data for analysis.

```

if elapsed_time > hr_sec:

    t_sec,vel_ms,dir_deg,b_temp_c,b_temp_f,pres_pa,alt_m,...\

    = np.loadtxt(open(filename, 'rb'),...)

```

The requested results, say wind power graph, windrose or wind speed plot were prepared and saved in the required format; .pdf and .csv.

```

d_air = pres_pa/(287.05*(b_temp_c+273.15))

b_leng = 1

cp = 0.4

ar = np.pi*(b_leng**2)

pwr = 0.5*d_air*ar*(vel_ms**3)*cp

av_alt = round(np.average(alt_m),2)

```

The .pdf file was initialised for writing. Here, each output result was placed on its own page along with the notes about the output.

```

with PdfPages(plt_fig) as pdf:

    font = {'family': 'monospace',

```

```

        'color': 'darkred',

        'weight': 'normal',

        'size': 16,

    }

    txt1 = 'Dedan Kimathi University of Technology ...'

    txt2 = 'Altitude = '+str(av_alt)+'m\n\nAir ... '

```

The main analysis task was done in this section and appended into the file as it was completed.

```

p_fig1 = plt.figure()

p_fig1.text(.1,.5,txt1, fontdict=font)

pdf.savefig()

plt.close()

:

plt.figure(figsize=(8,6))

plt.plot(t_sec,pwr,'g-', label='Power')

plt.title('Estimated Power vs Time Plot')

plt.ylabel('Power [MW]')

plt.xlabel('Time [sec]')

plt.legend(loc='upper left')

plt.grid()

pdf.savefig()

plt.close()

:

p_fig2 = plt.figure()

p_fig2.text(.1,.3,txt2, fontdict=font)

```

```
pdf.savefig()

plt.close()
```

In this section, the complete task was packed ready to be delivered to the subscriber.

```
csv_path = f_path+filename

plt_fig_path = f_path+plt_fig

msg.attach(MIMEText(body, 'plain'))

attach_csv = open(csv_path, "rb")

attach_plt_fig = open(plt_fig_path, "rb")

part1 = MIMEBase('application', 'octet-stream')

part2 = MIMEBase('application', 'octet-stream')

part1.set_payload((attach_csv).read())

part2.set_payload((attach_plt_fig).read())

encoders.encode_base64(part1)

encoders.encode_base64(part2)

part1.add_header('Content-Disposition', "attach_csv; ... )

part2.add_header('Content-Disposition', "attach_plt ... )

msg.attach(part1)

msg.attach(part2)
```

At this level, the system checked to confirm if it was still connected to the internet. If yes, it proceeded to deliver the results. If not, the system noted the problem to deliver the results when it was next possible. This was achieved as illustrated next.

```

try:

    web = 'https://www.google.com'

    dat = urllib.urlopen(web)

    print 'connected'

    server = smtplib.SMTP('smtp.gmail.com', 587)

    server.starttls()

    server.login(fromaddr, security)

    text = msg.as_string()

    server.sendmail(fromaddr, toaddr, text)

    server.quit()

except:

    pass

    print 'not connected'

```

This process was repeated every time the results were requested. The system kept logging wind data as it streamed in.

```

filename = 'Wind_Data_{}.csv'.format(time.strftime('...'))

plt_fig = 'Data_Plot_{}.pdf'.format(time.strftime('...'))

msbjct = 'WIND_DATA_&_ANALYSIS_{}'.format(time ...)

fil = open(filename, 'ab')

fields = ('t_sec', 'vel_ms', 'dir_deg', 'b_temp_c', ... )

wr = csv.DictWriter(fil, fieldnames=fields, ... )

wr.writeheader()

fil.close()

start = round(timer(),4)

```

3.7 Field Test

After sensors calibration and algorithm development, the complete system was retested in the lab. After successful the runs, it was taken to the field for a test; as seen in the attached Photo 2. The indoors central minicomputer received the data wirelessly and analysed it. This was done either in portions as requested by the subscriber or as long-term combined data, which was available for analysis after the station had collected data for a long time. All the analyses were automatically printed to a .pdf and/or a .png file format as an output and attached to an online user on request. The data used was also availed in a .csv document format. This is as seen in the attached Snapshot 3.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this chapter, all the data collected in this study is presented and analysed. In every part, detailed discussions about the presented data is included. Python programming language was intensively used in this chapter to carry out the required analysis.

4.1 Preliminary Experimental Results and Analysis

The following data plot was from the digital manual anemometer placed at points 1, 2 and 3 as shown in Figure 10 (b). The data used is as presented in Appendix A. This data was used to plot the three data points in tunnel test section, against the fan speed increments. The graphical results were as presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Wind Speed vs Fan Speed

From the graph of Figure 1, it was noted that point 1 and point 3 showed similar

results. Looking at the cross-section of the test section in Figure 10, it was expected that, from Bernoulli's principle in reference to points 1, 2, and 3;

$$A_1V_1 = A_2V_2 = A_3V_3 \quad (1)$$

Given that the area;

$$A_1 = A_2 = A_3 \quad (2)$$

The velocities should be equal as in;

$$V_1 = V_2 = V_3 \quad (3)$$

However, V_2 was observed to be very different from V_1 and V_3 . This is because during the experiment, point 2 was placed far away from point 1 and 3 where there was obstruction by the inbuilt sensor. This obstruction introduced interference that affected V_2 . This confirmed that the protrusion of the inbuilt wind sensor introduced turbulence within the wind tunnel starting from the test section. The data collected automatically by the inbuilt sensor was plotted as well. This data is presented in Appendix B. The graphical representation is as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Inbuilt Wind Speed vs Fan Speed

The two plots in Figure 2, auto run 1 and auto run 2 from the inbuilt wind sensor confirmed that this sensor can be relied upon since the plots are similar. However, as seen in the same figure 2, the same auto run showed significantly different results after 3 days. This implied that the same wind sensor would give different results for the same measurement after some time. This meant that calibration of the cup-vane anemometer should be done the same day, within the shortest time possible. The next exercise was to compare the data collected by the digital manual anemometer with that collected by the inbuilt wind sensor. The graphical results were as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Manual vs Inbuilt

The graph of Figure 3 captured the relationship between the inbuilt and the manual sensor. This plot confirmed that the digital manual anemometer and inbuilt wind sensor recorded different values for the same wind speed. This disparity was deterministic and hence tolerable. However, the manual anemometer was used in the rest of the experiment due to its ease of movement when measuring wind speed at the outlet; which was the key interest. Still, the curve for the manual anemometer was almost perfectly linear which was desirable during calibration IEC (2005); Kristensen (1999). The manual anemometer was hence used to collect the wind speed data at the outlet of the wind tunnel shown in Figure 10. The experimental setup was as shown in Figure 4. The collected data was as presented in Appendix C. This data was loaded in to the program and plotted in a graph shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4: Tunnel Outlet

The plot of Figure 5 was a representation of the wind speed across the outlet of the Armfield C15 radius, as seen in point 4 of Figure 4 and 10 (b); from 1.5in (3.81cm) to 8.5in (21.59cm) away from the centre.

Figure 5: Outlet Airflow Variation

From the plot of the Figure 5, it was deduced that at $0in$ to around $4in$ and around $7in$ to $8.5in$ from the centre of the outlet, an increase in fan speed did not result to a significant increase in wind speed. This was not suitable for cup-vane calibration. At $4.76in$ from the centre, significant increase in wind speed was observed as the fan rotation speed was varied from $16 - 70\%$. However, as the fan rotation speed was increased from $73 - 100\%$, this trend shifted to position $5.76in$ from the centre of the outlet. It can be seen that there was least turbulence between these two points. To verify that points $4.76in$ and $5.76in$ had the most desirable air flow for the cup-vane calibration, a plot of the air flow below, above and between points $4.76in$ and $5.76in$ was needed. The data that was collected is as presented in appendix D. This data was plotted as seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Airflow Below, Above and Between

Figure 6 showed that the points below and above are similar. They presented the lowest wind speeds and were highly turbulent. Point between was well linear, had the highest wind speed and it was least turbulent. During calibration, the cup-vane anemometer was hence placed directly between 4.76in and 5.76in. This point was named 'Point 4'. It was important to check the wind speed changes from the wind tunnel test section towards the wind tunnel outlet where the cup-vane anemometer was placed. This comparison is presented in Figure 7. The data used in this case is presented in E.

Figure 7: Comparison Between Test Section and Outlet at Point 4

From the plot of Figure 7, it was noted that from test point to the point of cup-vane anemometer calibration (point 4), the wind speed reduced by approximately a half. This, however, did not affect the calibration exercise.

4.2 Cup-Vane Anemometer Calibration Results

4.2.1 Cup Calibration Results and Analysis

The cup anemometer RPM was compared with the wind speed coming out of the wind tunnel at point 4. The results were as shown in Figure 8 below.

Figure 8: RPM vs Wind Speed

This comparison was important in the sense that it showed that the data collected from the wireless cup anemometer was linear and consistent. This made the calibration process much easier. Still, the relationship between the wireless anemometer and the manual anemometer could be found easily.

The next step was to perform the calibration. A graph of the cup-vane anemometer RPM versus the reference tunnel wind speed was plotted. A polynomial function that best fits within the scatter plotted data was calculated and the results plotted using a program. This was done in the Python program as briefly illustrated next.

```
In [16]: c_x = c_dat['wireless wind speed run4'];
        c_y = c_dat['manual wind speed run18']
        z = np.polyfit(c_x, c_y, 1); p = np.poly1d(z)
        slope, intercept, r_value, p_value, \
        slope_std_error = stats.linregress(c_x,p(c_x))
        x_1 = 12; y_1 = slope*x_1+intercept
        c_line = 'y={0:.2f}x+{1:.2f}'.format(z[0],z[1])
        calibrated_data = p(c_x)
        plt.scatter(c_x,c_y, label='wls cup-vane run', ... )
        plt.plot(c_x,p(c_x), color='k', label='trendline', ... )
        plt.annotate('y={0:.2f}x+{1:.2f}'.format(z[0],z[1]), ... )
        :
```

At this stage, the correlation coefficient between the plotted points and the polynomial of best fit was calculated as well. The calculated polyfit data was as presented in Appendix F. The The graphical results were as seen in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Calibration Graph

As seen from the plot of Figure 9, this relationship was linear. Most points fit within the trendline with an r-value of approximately 1. This meant that most points fit within the calculated polynomial of best fit and so this line could be relied upon; since it was well above the least expected r-value of 0.99995 IEC (2005). To check further, the null hypothesis was used. In this case, the null hypothesis was that ‘the scatter points had no relationship with the fitting polynomial’. After the calculation, the p-value returned a value close to 0; which implied high confidence in rejecting the null hypothesis. The slope standard error was also close to 0. Up to this point, the calibration exercise had returned positive results.

The resulting transfer function for the wireless 3D-Printed cup-vane anemometer is;

$$V[m/s] = 0.6478 \times CA[RPM] + 1.0164 \quad (4)$$

Where $V[m/s]$ is the wind speed and $CA[RPM]$ is the cup anemometer RPM. Equation 4 is similar to the cup anemometer Equation 5.

$$V = Af + B \quad (5)$$

Where A is the slope constant and B is the offset. Hence, the slope constant for this cup anemometer is 0.6478 while the offset is 1.0164.

Cup Anemometer Calibration Uncertainty

The next step was to find the uncertainty errors by calculating the residual differences. From the cup calibration calculation, residual calculation was done by taking $p(c_x) - c_y$. The calculated residuals data output was as shown in Appendix G. The residual wind speed was plotted against the Cup-Vane RPM as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Residuals Graph

The plot of the Figure 10 provided a clear visualisation of the calibration residual dif-

ferences. The maximum positive residual value (fitting deviation) was $+0.204084m/s$ while the minimum was $+0.001048m/s$. The maximum negative fitting deviation was $-0.174730m/s$ while the minimum was $-0.009122m/s$. The mean fitting deviation for positive and negative residuals was $\pm 0.063398m/s$.

After calibration, it was important to expose the calibrated anemometer to the wind tunnel and plot a graph of the calibrated data with that of the manual anemometer, both instruments measuring the wind speed at the same point. This is as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Calibrated Results

After calibration, the cup-vane anemometer presented very reliable data that reflected the true wind speed. At this point, the wireless cup anemometer was calibrated.

Cup Anemometer Hysterisis Loses

As recommended by IEC61400-12-1(2005) standards IEC (2005), it is important to check if the instrument suffers from hysteresis losses. The hysteresis data output was as shown in Appendix H.

A graph for the rising and falling data was plotted on the same axis as illustrated in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Hysterisis

Figure 12 shows two curves plotted using the wireless cup anemometer data as wind was varied from minimum to maximum (rising) and back from maximum to minimum (falling). The results in this graph presented negligible levels of hysteresis loss.

4.2.2 Vane Calibration Results and Analysis

A command was fired at the terminal to identify the HMC5883L I^2C address. The address for the sensor that was used in this study was found to be 0x1e. All the required libraries were then imported into the program to facilitate the calibration process.

In reference to HMC5883L datasheet Honeywell (March 2011) and some helpful online illustrations Bitify (Nov 17 2013); Instructables (July 14 2015), the sensor was prepared for data collection using a program. The next step was to print the sensor bearing as the sensor is rotated through roughly 0 – 90 – 180 – 270 – 360 degrees. As expected, the results were close to expectation but not exactly precise; due to manual turning.

Two sets of data carrying about 250 readings each were then collected and saved. Both data sets were collected as the sensor was rotated thorough out 360 degrees; one rotation per second for around 25 rotations clockwise and the same repeated for counterclockwise rotation. During rotations, the sensor was kept on the same level on a flat surface.

The same process to that of clockwise run was repeated to collect the second set of data for the counterclockwise run. The data output for the counterclockwise run is presented in Appendix J. This data set was similar to that of clockwise run.

The two sets of data were then loaded into Python, ready for analysis. For calibration purposes, data for X and Y_scaled was used. This data was plotted on the same area within a rectangle shown in the Figure 13.

Figure 13: HMC5883L Calibration Plot Space

Clockwise Rotation

The first set of data collected as the sensor is rotated clockwise was stored in a file and loaded into the program. This data was then plotted in a graph shown in Figure 13. The results were as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: HMC5883L CW Calibration Plot

From Figure 14, it can be seen that the data collected from the sensor was well represented throughout 360 degrees. Only one stray data point.

However, the this representation clearly showed that the sensor was offset.

Counterclockwise Rotation

The same technique as that of clockwise run above was used to plot the data for counterclockwise run. The output for this plot was as shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15: HMC5883L CCW Calibration Plot

Comparing Figure 14 and Figure 15, data for clockwise and counter clockwise moves is similar. It is off the centre by a similar amount of error. To correct this offset error, the offset amount was calculated using a program as the sensor was rotated back and forth through 360 degrees. This was done as illustrated next:

```
In [13]: xmin = 0; xmax = 0; ymin = 0; ymax = 0; sleep(3)

for i in range(0,250):

    x = read_word_2c(3); y = read_word_2c(7)

    z = read_word_2c(5)

    if x < xmin:

        xmin=x

    if y < ymin:

        ymin=y
```

```

        if x > xmax:
            xmax=x

        if y > ymax:
            ymax=y

        sleep(0.1)

        :

    print "x offset: ", (xmax + xmin) / 2

    print "y offset: ", (ymax + ymin) / 2

```

The results were as shown here:

```

xmin:  -628

ymin:  -814

xmax:  790

ymax:  662

x offset:  81

y offset:  -76

```

Offset Compensation

The wind vane in this case had offsets as shown by the output just above. The offsets were then incorporated into the program formula and data was collected again, as the sensor was rotated back and forth throughout 360 degrees. Around 250 sets of data were collected and saved in a file, as presented in Appendix K. This data was then loaded into the program and plotted on the same area as in Figure 13. The results were as shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: HMC5883L Calibrated Plot

Figure 16 showed that the calibrated sensor data was well centred. Data collected before and after calibration was plotted on the same axes. The output was as shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17: HMC5883L Comparison Plot

Looking at Figure 17, the final results shows that after calibration, the HMC5883L offset was taken care of and data did fit well at the centre, throughout 360 degrees rotation. The last thing to factor in was the magnetic declination, which varies depending on the location. This was found at <http://www.magnetic-declination.com/>. The wind vane was well calibrated.

4.3 Field Wind Resource Assessment Results

The results presented in this section are as was obtained automatically via a subscribed email address from the system installed in the field. The technical program illustrations presented were the key drive of the developed wind resource assessment system.

In real life, wind speed varies from time to time. The general characteristics that describe wind gust are as illustrated in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Discrete Gust Event Manwell et al. (2009)

Where a = amplitude, b = rise time, c = maximum gust variation, and d = lapse time.

The developed algorithm analysed the collected wind data as presented next.

4.3.1 Discussion and Data Presentation

To handle the collected data from wireless sensor nodes, the system first imported all the required libraries for wind data analysis to provide the necessary muscle for the task ahead. This was as illustrated next:

```
In [1]: import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

import numpy as np

import pandas as pd

from scipy import stats

from scipy.stats import rayleigh

from scipy.stats import dweibull

from windrose import WindroseAxes

%matplotlib inline
```

A collection database was made, from where data was loaded appropriately; ready for analysis. In this case, the analysis was done for all the data collected by the instrument during the field test:

```
In [3]: wdata = pd.concat([testpt1, testpt2, testpt3])

wvel = wdata['Wind Vel(m/s)']; wdir = wdata['dir(deg)'];

wtym = wdata['time(s)']; temp = wdata['temp(c)']; ...

wdata
```

For presentation, the data output 'Out [3]' for the input 'In [3]' just above is presented in Appendix L. This was the data collected wirelessly by the developed system installed in the field at *Lat, Lon*[-0.398613, 36.960662]; 70m away from the main station, 2.5m above the ground. These results were for 3hrs data.

4.3.2 Wind Speed Results and Analysis

Wind Speed Presentation

The first output that was provided by the system was the time versus speed plot as shown in Figure 19. This provided a quick view of the available wind at the prospected site. From this 5000sec plot, wind fluctuated from around 0.2m/s to around 4.7m/s. This graph also provided the mean wind speed; in this case 1.6m/s.

```
In [4]: plt.plot(wtym, wvel, 'b-', label='wind speed')  
  
        plt.hlines(wvel.mean(), ... )  
  
        plt.title('Time vs Wind Speed'); plt.xlabel('Time (sec)')  
  
        plt.ylabel('Wind Speed (m/s)'); plt.legend(loc='best')
```


Figure 19: Wind Speed vs Time Plot

Wind Speed Variation with Height

The second output was the wind power spectral density function. This plot illustrated the wind shear as shown in Figure 20. This phenomenon showed that mean wind speed increases with height. As discussed in James Manwell publication Manwell et al. (2009), this characteristic greatly influences wind resource assessment and design of installed wind turbine.

```
In [5]: plt.figure(figsize=(10,8)); plt.grid()

        power, freq = plt.psd(wvel, NFFT=256, Fs=2)

        plt.title('Wind Speed Power Spectral Density Function')
```


Figure 20: Wind PSDF

Wind Speed Probability Density Functions

The third most important output presented by the system was wind speed PDFs; which are essential in wind energy prediction. Gaussian, Rayleigh, and Weibull PDFs were used since they are the most commonly used PDFs in wind speed analysis. Here, the first step was to calculate and present the wind velocity mean, variance and standard deviation. This was done as illustrated next:

```
In [6]: print 'Mean Wind Speed:', wvel.mean()
        print 'Wind Speed Variance:', wvel.var()
        print 'Wind Speed Std Deviation:', wvel.std()
```

```
Mean Wind Speed: 1.55588969823
```

```
Wind Speed Variance: 0.404561733654
```

```
Wind Speed Std Deviation: 0.6360516753017635
```

Gaussian PDF The Gaussian PDF presented in Figure 21 showed the likelihood that wind speed is a certain value ($1.6m/s$). This was guided by the Gaussian Equation 6.

$$p(bins) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \times \exp\left[-\frac{(bins - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right] \quad (6)$$

Where μ (μ) represented the mean and σ (σ) the standard deviation. Variance was σ squared (σ^2).

```
In [7]: s = np.random.normal(mu,sigma,1000)

count,bins,ignored = plt.hist(s,30,normed=True)

plt.plot(bins,

1/(sigma*np.sqrt(2*np.pi))*np.exp(-(bins-mu)**2/(2*sigma**2)))
```


Figure 21: Wind Gaussian PDF

Rayleigh PDF For the same purpose as Gaussian PDF, IEC61400-12-1 standards IEC (2005) recommends the Rayleigh PDF. This PDF is guided by Equation 7. The Rayleigh distributions were presented as shown in Figure 22.

$$p(U) = \frac{\pi}{2} \times \left(\frac{U}{U_{mean}} \right) \times \exp \left[-\frac{\pi}{4} \times \left(\frac{U}{U_{mean}} \right)^2 \right] \quad (7)$$

For Rayleigh distributions, mean is the key parameter. These distributions were plotted for different values of mean, on the same axis.

```
In [8]: wv_m = wvel.mean()

mean = rayleigh.stats(moments='m')

plt.scatter(wvel,

(np.pi/2)*(wvel/mean**2)*np.exp(-(np.pi/4)*(wvel/mean)**2)...
```


Figure 22: Wind Rayleigh PDF

Weibull PDF For Weibull distribution, there are only two key parameters; the shape factor k and the scale factor λ (λ). This was plotted as shown in Figure 23. The Weibull function takes the form shown in Equation 8.

$$p(x) = \frac{k}{\lambda} \times \left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^{k-1} \times \exp\left[-\left(\frac{x}{\lambda}\right)^k\right] \quad (8)$$

```
In [9]: k_values = [0.5, 1, 2, 2]; lam_values = [1, 1, 1, 2]

color = ['k', 'b', 'g', 'r']; mu = 0; x = wvel

for (k, lam, clr) in zip(k_values, lam_values, color):

    dist = dweibull(k, mu, lam)

    plt.scatter(x, dist.pdf(x), marker='s', color=clr,...)

plt.xlabel('Wind Speed (m/s)'); plt.ylabel('Distribution');...
```


Figure 23: Wind Weibull PDF

4.3.3 Wind Direction Results and Analysis

Scatter Plot

The wind direction scatter plot output of Figure 24 showed the details about how the wind direction varied within the 5000sec. From this plot, wind was prevalent at 345° and later at around 150°.

```
In [10]: ax=plt.subplot(111, projection='polar')  
  
ax.scatter(np.deg2rad(wdir),wtym,s=8,marker='s', color='b')  
  
ax.set_rmax(max(wtym))  
  
ax.set_xticks(np.linspace(0, 2*np.pi, 24, endpoint=False))  
  
ax.set_theta_direction(-1); ax.set_theta_offset(np.pi/2.0)
```


Figure 24: Wind Polar Scatter Plot

Windrose Plot

As shown in Figure 25, Windrose output showed the wind frequency distribution in a certain direction. This is the most commonly used wind direction plot. From this plot, the best direction to orient a wind turbine in the prospected site would be NN-W; where wind speeds ranging from $1m/s$ to $1.9m/s$ are expected.

```
In [11]: def new_axes():  
  
         rect = [0.1, 0.1, 0.8, 0.8]  
  
         ax = WindroseAxes(fig, rect, axisbg='w')  
  
         fig.add_axes(ax); return ax  
  
ax = new_axes(); ax.bar(wdir, wvel, normed=1,...)
```


Figure 25: Windrose Plot

4.3.4 Wind Energy Results and Analysis

The developed system was also able to provide the wind energy prediction results as illustrated here. The available wind power was estimated using Equation 9 in reference to RWE Npower Renewables Renewable (2010).

$$P_{wind} = \frac{1}{2} \times \rho AV^3 C_p \quad (9)$$

Where ρ represented the air density (av_d_air), A represented the area swept by the turbine blade (ar), V the wind speed (wvel), and C_p the power coefficient (cp). The system presented the calculated wind power from wind data, and the parameters values in Equation 9.

```
In [12]: d_air = pres/(287.05*(temp+273.15))
        av_d_air = np.average(d_air);
        print 'Air Density (kg/m^3):', av_d_air
        b_leng = 1; print 'Blade Length (m):', b_leng
        cp = 0.4; print 'Power Coefficient:', cp
        ar = np.pi*(b_leng**2); print 'Swept Area (m^2):', ar
        pwr = 0.5*av_d_air*ar*(wvel**3)*cp
        av_alt = round(np.average(alt),2);
        print 'Altitude (m):', av_alt
```

Air Density (kg/m³): 0.9586171958491977

Blade Length (m): 1

Power Coefficient: 0.4

Swept Area (m²): 3.14159265359

Altitude (m): 1723.74

Figure 26 shows the estimated power (calculated) output, plotted against wind speed. From this plot, the developed system suggests that a wind power of around 1MW can reliably be extracted from the prospected site.

```
In [13]: plt.scatter(wvel,pwr,marker='s', label='Wind Power')

plt.title('Estimated Power vs Time Plot')

plt.ylabel('Power (MW)')

plt.xlabel('Wind Speed (m/s)')
```


Figure 26: Wind Power Plot

This wind power output was taken in consideration with the instrument uncertainty as presented in Figure 10. It is important to note that the actual wind energy extracted from this wind power varies widely depending on the characteristics of the installed wind turbine.

4.3.5 Other Results

From the data that the system collected from the field, as seen in Appendix L, the system can be made to provide more insights from the collected data. A case in point is that of the output presented by Figure 27. This plot showed rapid rise and fall of the temperature at the prospected site. A likely cause is that the sun shine was rapidly covered by the clouds. These changes in temperature affect frictional torque of the cup-vane instrument. However, the aerodynamic torque is much higher than the frictional torque effect. Frictional torque is usually neglected Pindado et al. (2014).

```
In [14]: plt.figure(figsize=(10,8)); plt.grid()

plt.plot(wtym, temp,'r-', linewidth=2.5, label='Wind Temp')

plt.title('Time vs Wind Temperature'); plt.xlabel('Time (sec)')

plt.ylabel('Temp (deg)'); plt.legend(loc='best')
```


Figure 27: Wind Temperature Plot

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

This study gave rise to a wireless 3D-Printed Cup-Vane Anemometer capable of transmitting wind data wirelessly via IEEE 802.15.4 protocol into a central station located up to 100m away. This implementation represents one sensor node capable of transmitting wind direction, wind speed, temperature, humidity, pressure and altitude. More such instrument nodes can be installed at different points and made to transmit to the same central station via a wireless sensor network.

The developed cup anemometer was found to be governed by a specific calibration function presented by Equation 4. Further calculations showed that the developed 3D-Printed wireless anemometer had a maximum positive residual value (fitting deviation) of $+0.204084m/s$ while the minimum was $+0.001048m/s$. The maximum negative fitting deviation was $-0.174730m/s$ while the minimum was $-0.009122m/s$. The mean fitting deviation for positive and negative residuals was $\pm 0.063398m/s$. This is as illustrated by the residuals results of Figure 10. The wind vane developed recorded an x-offset of 81 and a y-offset of -76 before calibration.

During laboratory tests, the calibrated Cup-Vane Anemometer consistently provided the expected results. The developed Cup-Vane Anemometer is therefore a reliable instrument that can successfully be used for wind resource assessment. In addition, the embedded electronics used in this system are low power, which makes it economical

since the installed system can comfortably run on a battery for an year.

Gauging from the field data which was automatically collected and analysed, it can be deduced that the developed IoT system for WRA tests successful. When carrying out a WRA for the prospected wind farm, a system like the one developed in this study could cut down on the costs involved during a normal WRA exercise. This is because after installation of the instruments in a distant site, the wind farmer sits and waits for the system to do all the tedious tasks, then deliver the requested results.

After the Cup-Vane Anemometer parts are well designed, it becomes easy to have as many Cup-Vane Anemometers as are needed, since the remaining exercise is only printing the parts on a 3D-Printer. This is probably the cheapest way of obtaining a Cup-Vane Anemometer that is within the researcher's known standards.

5.2 Recommendations

For the Cup-Vane Anemometer design, it is recommended that numerous cups and vanes be printed and tested for optimal conditions that could possibly improve the performance of the existing one.

When performing Cup Anemometer calibration, it is recommended that a wind tunnel specifically designed for Cup Anemometer calibration be used. This can significantly reduce the number of experiments needed to complete the calibration exercise.

The developed wireless station responded well within around 100m. The wireless

communication did not test reliable beyond this distance. If need be, more powerful radios such as XBee Pro can be used in place of the existing one to improve on the communication distance.

To improve on wind data analysis and processing, updates can be done to include topographical and site roughness inputs. To maximise on the developed sensor node, it would be great to add such sensors as solar intensity and rain gauge in the next iteration.

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APPENDIX ONE

WIND TUNNEL TEST SECTION DATA — MANUAL

	fn_spd	mnl_wspd_rn1	mnl_wspd_rn2	mnl_wspd_rn3
0	13	3.1000	2.7000	3.1143
1	16	3.8857	3.3714	3.9000
2	19	4.5857	4.0143	4.6000
3	22	5.3286	4.6286	5.3857
4	25	6.0857	5.2571	6.1286
5	28	6.7286	5.8286	6.8000
6	31	7.5000	6.3571	7.5429
7	34	8.2286	6.9571	8.3143
8	37	8.7286	7.5714	9.0143
9	40	9.2571	8.1429	9.7714
10	43	10.0857	8.7143	10.4000
11	46	10.6857	9.3000	11.0000
12	49	11.4571	9.8714	11.6857
13	52	12.0714	10.3571	12.3143
14	55	12.8571	10.9286	12.9286
15	58	13.5000	11.4000	13.7714
16	61	14.1429	12.0429	14.4000
17	64	14.7429	12.4714	14.9429
18	67	15.2571	12.9286	15.4857
19	70	15.7571	13.3143	16.0000
20	73	16.3000	13.8286	16.5143
21	76	16.9714	14.4714	17.2714
22	79	17.9286	15.0714	18.0143
23	82	18.7429	15.7857	18.8286
24	85	19.5429	16.4714	19.7000
25	88	20.4857	17.1714	20.5571
26	91	21.2143	17.9000	21.4714
27	94	22.1571	18.5571	22.3571
28	97	22.8857	19.3000	23.0857
29	100	23.5143	19.9714	23.9714

APPENDIX TWO

WIND TUNNEL TEST SECTION DATA — AUTO

	fn_spd	a_wspd_rn1	a_wspd_rn2	a_wspd_rn3
0	13	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
1	16	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
2	19	0.7473	1.0888	0.0000
3	22	3.2440	3.2846	2.8862
4	25	4.6818	4.6247	4.2874
5	28	5.7723	5.8195	5.2805
6	31	6.7281	6.7692	6.4183
7	34	7.6182	7.6362	7.3461
8	37	8.5261	8.4941	8.2513
9	40	9.4331	9.3753	8.9911
10	43	10.1941	10.3261	9.7582
11	46	11.1478	10.9883	10.6241
12	49	11.9243	11.8561	11.3886
13	52	12.6962	12.6857	12.0151
14	55	13.4240	13.4138	12.8656
15	58	14.1904	14.2290	13.7141
16	61	14.9817	14.8455	14.4084
17	64	15.5770	15.5243	15.1705
18	67	16.3472	16.2498	15.5845
19	70	17.0339	16.9852	16.3008
20	73	17.6675	17.6982	16.9935
21	76	18.6468	18.5366	17.9872
22	79	19.5074	19.4172	19.0002
23	82	20.4386	20.4386	19.8047
24	85	21.4056	21.3480	20.6368
25	88	22.2876	22.2932	21.7140
26	91	23.2535	23.2475	22.6505
27	94	24.1863	24.0678	23.3639
28	97	25.1113	25.0946	24.2704
29	100	25.9559	25.9562	25.1762

APPENDIX THREE

WIND TUNNEL OUTLET DATA

	fn_spd	@1.5in	@2.5in	@3.5in	@4.5in	@5.5in	@6.5in	@7.5in	@8.5in
0	13	0.8143	0.8571	0.8571	0.8286	1.6857	0.8571	0.8714	0.8429
1	16	0.9000	0.9000	0.9000	2.1571	2.0857	1.6429	0.9000	0.9000
2	19	1.0000	1.0000	1.0714	2.7000	2.4857	1.9429	1.0000	1.0000
3	22	1.0857	1.1000	1.3571	3.1143	2.8286	2.2429	1.1000	1.1000
4	25	1.1571	1.1429	1.6143	3.4429	3.1714	2.6000	1.0571	1.0714
5	28	1.2000	1.2000	1.9714	3.8571	3.5714	2.8429	1.0000	1.1429
6	31	1.3000	1.3000	2.1000	4.2714	3.9286	3.1714	1.2000	1.4286
7	34	1.4000	1.4000	2.2571	4.6714	4.2429	3.5000	1.9714	1.7286
8	37	1.4571	1.4714	2.6714	5.0143	4.6143	3.7857	2.0000	1.9429
9	40	1.5000	1.5000	2.5000	5.4857	4.9857	4.1000	2.1429	2.0286
10	43	1.6000	1.6000	2.4429	5.8286	5.3429	4.4571	2.2571	2.2000
11	46	1.7000	1.7000	2.3714	6.1857	5.7143	4.6571	2.4714	2.3571
12	49	1.7571	1.7429	2.3143	6.6286	6.1000	4.9714	2.6429	2.5000
13	52	1.8000	1.8000	2.1714	6.9143	6.2429	5.2286	2.8714	2.6286
14	55	1.9000	1.9000	2.2571	7.1571	6.5857	5.5286	3.0429	2.7429
15	58	2.0000	2.0000	2.1000	7.4286	6.9000	5.8143	3.0857	2.9714
16	61	2.0000	2.0000	2.1429	7.6286	7.1286	6.0000	3.1286	3.0857
17	64	2.1000	2.1000	2.1429	7.7000	7.3714	6.2286	3.0714	3.0286
18	67	2.1429	2.1286	2.2286	7.5857	7.6857	6.4286	3.2286	3.1000
19	70	2.2000	2.2000	2.2286	7.3143	7.8857	6.6714	3.2286	3.2714
20	73	2.3000	2.3000	2.3000	5.9857	8.2000	6.9429	3.2857	3.2714
21	76	2.4000	2.3857	2.4000	5.8143	8.4429	7.2286	3.4714	3.5000
22	79	2.4571	2.4571	2.4714	6.0429	8.8000	7.4714	3.8286	3.6286
23	82	2.5000	2.5000	2.5000	6.2000	9.1429	7.8000	3.8714	3.8286
24	85	2.6000	2.6000	2.6000	5.9000	9.6000	8.1286	3.9429	3.9571
25	88	2.7000	2.7000	2.7000	5.7286	9.9857	8.4000	4.0286	4.1286
26	91	2.7429	2.7429	2.7571	5.7857	10.2714	8.7143	4.0143	4.2286
27	94	2.8000	2.8000	2.8000	6.2857	10.5714	8.9714	4.3857	4.2857
28	97	2.9000	2.9000	2.9143	6.9000	10.8714	9.2714	4.2286	4.4571
29	100	3.0000	3.0000	3.0000	6.3286	11.2429	9.5286	4.2429	4.5429

APPENDIX FOUR

WIND DATA AROUND POINT 4

	blw_rn1	blw_rn2	blw_rn3	abv_rn1	abv_rn2	abv_rn3	btn_rn1	btn_rn2	\
0	0.8429	0.8571	0.8429	0.8571	0.8429	0.8714	1.8286	1.8571	
1	0.9000	0.9000	1.0000	0.9000	0.9000	0.9000	2.2286	2.2857	
2	1.0000	1.0000	0.9429	1.0000	0.9714	1.0000	2.6286	2.7000	
3	1.0000	1.0571	1.0000	1.0000	1.0571	0.9857	3.0429	3.1000	
4	1.2714	0.9857	1.2857	0.9571	1.0143	1.1714	3.5000	3.4857	
5	1.3143	1.1714	1.2000	1.2429	1.0571	1.5143	3.8143	3.9143	
6	1.6857	1.4571	1.4571	1.5000	1.4143	1.4571	4.1429	4.2286	
7	1.7429	1.3857	1.9143	1.6714	1.5286	1.7429	4.5000	4.4857	
8	2.0286	1.8857	2.1286	1.7857	1.7143	1.9714	4.8286	4.7857	
9	2.3857	2.2000	2.2571	2.1143	1.8857	2.0571	5.1857	5.1571	
10	2.5000	2.1429	2.1143	2.2000	2.3571	2.2714	5.5286	5.5143	
11	2.5857	2.4286	2.3714	2.6000	2.2571	2.5429	5.8000	5.9143	
12	2.7714	2.6143	2.8714	2.4429	2.3857	2.6571	6.1143	6.1429	
13	3.1714	2.6571	3.2714	2.6714	2.7286	2.8429	6.3000	6.3714	
14	3.0714	2.8571	3.3714	3.0143	2.9714	2.9286	6.7429	6.6857	
15	3.1571	2.8857	3.2571	3.3857	3.1571	3.0571	7.0429	7.0857	
16	3.4857	3.4429	2.9429	3.5571	3.4429	3.4000	7.3857	7.3286	
17	3.4857	3.4286	3.4286	3.8429	3.4000	3.2571	7.5571	7.5714	
18	3.6286	3.4714	3.6571	3.7857	3.6000	3.3000	7.7714	7.8571	
19	3.8286	3.9714	3.3000	3.9286	3.1429	3.4429	8.1000	8.1000	
20	4.1286	3.8143	3.5286	4.0000	3.9714	3.8857	8.2571	8.2571	
21	4.1000	3.7571	4.2571	4.2429	4.4714	4.1714	8.5286	8.4857	
22	4.2000	4.2143	4.2714	4.0714	4.5857	3.9714	8.9571	8.9857	
23	5.0857	4.2000	5.0857	4.3714	4.8286	4.3714	9.3429	9.1571	
24	4.8286	4.4143	5.1286	4.8143	4.2000	4.7000	9.4571	9.6429	
25	4.9429	4.9571	5.0857	4.4143	4.9571	4.7286	10.1143	10.1429	
26	5.6000	5.1429	5.4857	4.8000	5.0000	5.0571	10.3714	10.4429	
27	5.2571	4.9429	5.7571	5.6571	5.6857	5.5143	10.7143	10.8286	
28	5.9143	5.5857	6.1429	5.8286	5.8286	5.5000	11.3000	11.2857	
29	6.4143	5.5857	5.6429	5.2286	6.3714	5.3857	11.4714	11.4857	

	btn_rn3
0	1.7000
1	2.1429
2	2.5143
3	3.0000
4	3.4286
5	3.7714
6	4.0714
7	4.4429
8	4.7286
9	5.1429
10	5.4429
11	5.6857
12	6.0857
13	6.3429
14	6.6429
15	7.0000
16	7.2143
17	7.4571
18	7.6000
19	8.1286
20	8.2429
21	8.4571
22	9.0000
23	9.2000
24	9.6286
25	10.0714
26	10.4571
27	10.7857
28	11.2000
29	11.5857

APPENDIX FIVE

CUP ANEMOMETER VS POINT 4 DATA

	fn_spd	wls_cup_rn1	wls_cup_rn2	pt4_rn1	pt4_rn2
0	13	1.2614	1.2214	1.8286	1.7714
1	16	1.9586	1.8571	2.2286	2.1857
2	19	2.6286	2.5043	2.6286	2.5857
3	22	3.3043	3.1857	3.0429	3.0571
4	25	3.7471	3.7100	3.5000	3.5429
5	28	4.3657	4.3543	3.8143	3.8286
6	31	4.9400	4.9700	4.1429	4.2286
7	34	5.3629	5.3471	4.5000	4.5429
8	37	5.8343	5.9900	4.8286	4.9143
9	40	6.4414	6.4500	5.1857	5.1714
10	43	6.9343	6.9729	5.5286	5.4857
11	46	7.2943	7.3857	5.8000	5.7571
12	49	7.8414	7.8100	6.1143	6.1286
13	52	8.2843	8.2457	6.3000	6.4143
14	55	8.7071	8.8086	6.7429	6.6714
15	58	9.2671	9.0943	7.0429	7.1000
16	61	9.6529	9.5757	7.3857	7.2857
17	64	9.9800	10.0557	7.5571	7.6429
18	67	10.4729	10.3414	7.7714	8.0714
19	70	10.8286	10.8000	8.1000	8.2571
20	73	11.2814	11.2186	8.2571	8.4429
21	76	11.8257	11.9000	8.5286	8.4857
22	79	12.2671	12.3114	8.9571	9.0000
23	82	12.9614	12.9757	9.3429	9.3571
24	85	13.5271	13.3443	9.4571	9.7429
25	88	14.0671	14.0086	10.1143	10.1000
26	91	14.7386	14.6000	10.3714	10.4429
27	94	15.2914	14.8943	10.7143	10.9000
28	97	15.6171	15.6043	11.3000	11.1143
29	100	16.2471	16.0671	11.4714	11.5714

APPENDIX SIX

POLYFIT CALIBRATION DATA

	x_polyfit	y_polyfit
0	1.2214	1.807656
1	1.8571	2.219478
2	2.5043	2.638751
3	3.1857	3.080180
4	3.7100	3.419835
5	4.3543	3.837229
6	4.9700	4.236096
7	5.3471	4.480391
8	5.9900	4.896878
9	6.4500	5.194878
10	6.9729	5.533626
11	7.3857	5.801048
12	7.8100	6.075921
13	8.2457	6.358179
14	8.8086	6.722840
15	9.0943	6.907924
16	9.5757	7.219787
17	10.0557	7.530744
18	10.3414	7.715827
19	10.8000	8.012920
20	11.2186	8.284100
21	11.9000	8.725529
22	12.3114	8.992044
23	12.9757	9.422395
24	13.3443	9.661184
25	14.0086	10.091534
26	14.6000	10.474659
27	14.8943	10.665314
28	15.6043	11.125270
29	16.0671	11.425084

APPENDIX SEVEN

CUP ANEMOMETER UNCERTAINTY DATA

Out [18]:	Ref Speed (m/s)	Cup-Vane speed (m/s)	Residual (m/s)
0	1.8286	1.807656	-0.020944
1	2.2286	2.219478	-0.009122
2	2.6286	2.638751	0.010151
3	3.0429	3.080180	0.037280
4	3.5000	3.419835	-0.080165
5	3.8143	3.837229	0.022929
6	4.1429	4.236096	0.093196
7	4.5000	4.480391	-0.019609
8	4.8286	4.896878	0.068278
9	5.1857	5.194878	0.009178
10	5.5286	5.533626	0.005026
11	5.8000	5.801048	0.001048
12	6.1143	6.075921	-0.038379
13	6.3000	6.358179	0.058179
14	6.7429	6.722840	-0.020060
15	7.0429	6.907924	-0.134976
16	7.3857	7.219787	-0.165913
17	7.5571	7.530744	-0.026356
18	7.7714	7.715827	-0.055573
19	8.1000	8.012920	-0.087080
20	8.2571	8.284100	0.027000
21	8.5286	8.725529	0.196929
22	8.9571	8.992044	0.034944
23	9.3429	9.422395	0.079495
24	9.4571	9.661184	0.204084
25	10.1143	10.091534	-0.022766
26	10.3714	10.474659	0.103259
27	10.7143	10.665314	-0.048986
28	11.3000	11.125270	-0.174730
29	11.4714	11.425084	-0.046316

APPENDIX EIGHT

CUP ANEMOMETER HYSTERESIS DATA

```
Out [22]:
```

	rising (m/s)	falling (m/s)
0	0.000000	12.394286
1	0.285000	11.130000
2	1.406667	9.571250
3	2.500000	8.598571
4	3.640000	7.458333
5	4.420000	6.360000
6	5.262500	5.300000
7	6.430000	4.570000
8	7.601667	3.640000
9	8.654286	2.523333
10	9.705000	1.386667
11	11.277143	0.185000
12	12.394286	0.000000

APPENDIX NINE

HMC5883L CALIBRATION PREPARATION

```
In [4]: bus = smbus.SMBus(1)
        address = 0x1e
        def read_byte(adr):
            return bus.read_byte_data(address, adr)
        def read_word(adr):
            high = bus.read_byte_data(address, adr)
            low = bus.read_byte_data(address, adr+1)
            val = (high << 8) + low
            return val
        def read_word_2c(adr):
            val = read_word(adr)
            if (val >= 0x8000):
                return -((65535 - val) + 1)
            else:
                return val
        def write_byte(adr, value):
            bus.write_byte_data(address, adr, value)
        if __name__ == "__main__":
            write_byte(0, 0b01110000)
            write_byte(1, 0b00100000)
            write_byte(2, 0b00000000)
            scale = 0.92
```

APPENDIX TEN

HMC5883L DATA BEFORE CALIBRATION

```
Out [9] :      X    Y  X_scaled  Y_scaled  Bearing
0      673 -457   619.16  -420.44  325.821573
1      778  -28   715.76   -25.76  357.938831
2      642  364   590.64   334.88  29.552291
3      342  598   314.64   550.16  60.234486
4      342  598   314.64   550.16  60.234486
5     -361  486  -332.12   447.12  126.604904
6     -570  194  -524.40   178.48  161.203948
7     -622  -54  -572.24   -49.68  184.961791
8     -532 -438  -489.44  -402.96  219.464909
9     -532 -438  -489.44  -402.96  219.464909
10    -283 -700  -260.36  -644.00  247.987220
11      17 -800    15.64  -736.00  271.217352
12     351 -745   322.92  -685.40  295.227044
13     351 -745   322.92  -685.40  295.227044
14     351 -745   322.92  -685.40  295.227044
15     778 -107   715.76   -98.44  352.169117
16     700  270   644.00   248.40  21.092340
17     317  610   291.64   561.20  62.540357
18     317  610   291.64   561.20  62.540357
19    -224  573  -206.08   527.16  111.351769
20    -506  325  -465.52   299.00  147.287671
21    -603   84  -554.76    77.28  172.069534
22    -576 -341  -529.92  -313.72  210.626122
23    -576 -341  -529.92  -313.72  210.626122
24    -334 -667  -307.28  -613.64  243.400599
25     121 -802   111.32  -737.84  278.579668
26     466 -681   428.72  -626.52  304.383361
27     466 -681   428.72  -626.52  304.383361
28     466 -681   428.72  -626.52  304.383361
29     779  -18   716.68   -16.56  358.676328
...     ...   ...     ...     ...     ...
```

220	-577	-341	-530.84	-313.72	210.582572
221	-380	-629	-349.60	-578.68	238.862418
222	-380	-629	-349.60	-578.68	238.862418
223	-380	-629	-349.60	-578.68	238.862418
224	436	-699	401.12	-643.08	301.953779
225	741	-310	681.72	-285.20	337.297829
226	754	125	693.68	115.00	9.413025
227	754	125	693.68	115.00	9.413025
228	525	491	483.00	451.72	43.083337
229	-106	613	-97.52	563.96	99.810575
230	-495	343	-455.40	315.56	145.280778
231	-622	-49	-572.24	-45.08	184.504352
232	-622	-49	-572.24	-45.08	184.504352
233	-580	-335	-533.60	-308.20	210.010138
234	-379	-630	-348.68	-579.60	238.969418
235	33	-801	30.36	-736.92	272.359166
236	33	-801	30.36	-736.92	272.359166
237	33	-801	30.36	-736.92	272.359166
238	730	-341	671.60	-313.72	334.961627
239	752	133	691.84	122.36	10.029711
240	621	388	571.32	356.96	31.997089
241	621	388	571.32	356.96	31.997089
242	45	644	41.40	592.48	86.002910
243	-490	350	-450.80	322.00	144.462322
244	-613	40	-563.96	36.80	176.266580
245	-597	-276	-549.24	-253.92	204.811646
246	-597	-276	-549.24	-253.92	204.811646
247	-470	-529	-432.40	-486.68	228.379909
248	-211	-740	-194.12	-680.80	254.085287
249	162	-795	149.04	-731.40	281.517676

[250 rows x 5 columns]

APPENDIX ELEVEN

HMC5883L DATA AFTER CALIBRATION

```
Out [19]:
```

	X	Y	X_scaled	Y_scaled	Bearing
0	-348	642	-320.16	590.64	118.460176
1	-658	266	-605.36	244.72	157.988717
2	-701	-104	-644.92	-95.68	188.438817
3	-701	-104	-644.92	-95.68	188.438817
4	-625	-351	-575.00	-322.92	209.318567
5	-465	-562	-427.80	-517.04	230.395572
6	-239	-696	-219.88	-640.32	251.048000
7	41	-736	37.72	-677.12	273.188453
8	41	-736	37.72	-677.12	273.188453
9	373	-626	343.16	-575.92	300.788458
10	626	-342	575.92	-314.64	331.351078
11	703	117	646.76	107.64	9.449105
12	703	117	646.76	107.64	9.449105
13	703	117	646.76	107.64	9.449105
14	-124	727	-114.08	668.84	99.679447
15	-506	516	-465.52	474.72	134.439394
16	-630	324	-579.60	298.08	152.783888
17	-630	324	-579.60	298.08	152.783888
18	-630	324	-579.60	298.08	152.783888
19	-687	-179	-632.04	-164.68	194.603897
20	-614	-372	-564.88	-342.24	211.210130
21	-362	-640	-333.04	-588.80	240.506414
22	-362	-640	-333.04	-588.80	240.506414
23	18	-738	16.56	-678.96	271.397181
24	336	-648	309.12	-596.16	297.407575
25	618	-357	568.56	-328.44	329.986267
26	618	-357	568.56	-328.44	329.986267
27	618	-357	568.56	-328.44	329.986267
28	566	452	520.72	415.84	38.610394
29	214	706	196.88	649.52	73.137096
..

220	690	-168	634.80	-154.56	346.315980
221	632	345	581.44	317.40	28.629512
222	632	345	581.44	317.40	28.629512
223	632	345	581.44	317.40	28.629512
224	-243	692	-223.56	636.64	109.349034
225	-534	483	-491.28	444.36	137.870835
226	-707	11	-650.44	10.12	179.108624
227	-707	11	-650.44	10.12	179.108624
228	-707	11	-650.44	10.12	179.108624
229	-485	-543	-446.20	-499.56	228.229218
230	-233	-697	-214.36	-641.24	251.515743
231	30	-735	27.60	-676.20	272.337306
232	30	-735	27.60	-676.20	272.337306
233	360	-631	331.20	-580.52	299.705752
234	675	-219	621.00	-201.48	342.024633
235	687	186	632.04	171.12	15.149212
236	687	186	632.04	171.12	15.149212
237	687	186	632.04	171.12	15.149212
238	105	732	96.60	673.44	81.837026
239	-391	614	-359.72	564.88	122.489303
240	-644	305	-592.48	280.60	154.657649
241	-644	305	-592.48	280.60	154.657649
242	-704	-77	-647.68	-70.84	186.241914
243	-609	-379	-560.28	-348.68	211.895313
244	-392	-619	-360.64	-569.48	237.654759
245	-75	-733	-69.00	-674.36	264.157871
246	-75	-733	-69.00	-674.36	264.157871
247	293	-671	269.56	-617.32	293.589051
248	589	-409	541.88	-376.28	325.223992
249	708	33	651.36	30.36	2.668635

[250 rows x 5 columns]

APPENDIX TWELVE

FIELD TEST WIND DATA

```
Out [3]:
```

	time(s)	Wind Vel(m/s)	dir(deg)	temp(c)	pres(pa)	alt(m)
0	0	1.13	333.06	25.6	82271	1722.47
1	5	2.35	329.73	25.6	82269	1723.46
2	10	1.55	339.46	25.6	82261	1723.85
3	15	1.32	217.62	25.6	82269	1723.75
4	20	1.38	337.80	25.6	82269	1722.87
5	25	1.46	333.89	25.6	82271	1723.26
6	30	1.03	335.32	25.7	82270	1723.06
7	35	1.54	337.49	25.7	82271	1722.47
8	40	1.82	338.45	25.7	82272	1723.16
9	45	1.80	338.60	25.7	82270	1722.37
10	50	0.98	341.39	25.7	82269	1722.47
11	55	0.32	342.19	25.8	82270	1723.36
12	60	0.51	340.10	25.8	82270	1723.36
13	65	0.80	338.78	25.8	82264	1723.66
14	70	1.76	338.03	25.8	82262	1723.66
15	75	1.62	339.04	25.9	82262	1723.66
16	80	1.72	340.60	25.9	82272	1723.36
17	85	1.19	341.86	25.9	82271	1722.87
18	90	0.72	341.94	25.9	82272	1723.66
19	95	0.58	341.74	25.9	82269	1722.57
20	100	0.43	341.87	25.9	82269	1723.06
21	105	0.47	342.05	26.0	82271	1723.46
22	110	0.86	342.01	26.0	82269	1723.26
23	115	1.25	340.02	26.0	82263	1722.97
24	120	1.86	341.34	26.0	82267	1723.46
25	125	1.61	340.64	26.0	82270	1723.36
26	130	1.68	340.73	26.1	82270	1724.15
27	135	1.27	339.22	26.1	82267	1722.47
28	140	2.35	336.02	26.1	82265	1723.66
29	145	1.96	338.70	26.1	82265	1722.77
..

334	4655	1.30	122.72	22.1	82266	1722.77
335	4660	1.58	144.48	22.1	82269	1722.18
336	4665	1.13	137.85	22.0	82267	1722.67
337	4670	1.18	137.77	22.0	82265	1722.47
338	4675	1.25	136.00	22.0	82279	1722.77
339	4680	1.19	143.48	22.0	82270	1722.18
340	4685	0.74	145.98	22.0	82275	1722.77
341	4690	1.32	53.70	22.0	82272	1723.36
342	4695	1.86	145.99	22.0	82273	1723.06
343	4700	1.04	127.38	22.0	82271	1723.66
344	4705	1.68	144.65	22.0	82273	1722.47
345	4710	1.18	135.99	21.9	82270	1723.16
346	4715	1.35	142.25	21.9	82274	1722.37
347	4720	1.12	126.99	21.9	82273	1722.37
348	4725	1.32	145.00	21.9	82271	1722.97
349	4730	1.28	115.22	21.9	82270	1723.06
350	4735	1.48	139.75	21.9	82270	1722.77
351	4740	1.58	103.54	21.9	82266	1723.56
352	4745	1.80	66.95	21.9	82274	1722.37
353	4750	1.15	139.93	21.9	82276	1722.87
354	4755	1.38	57.61	21.9	82272	1721.68
355	4760	2.05	124.15	21.8	82274	1723.46
356	4765	1.43	140.68	21.8	82269	1723.26
357	4770	1.09	146.67	21.8	82272	1722.57
358	4775	2.33	144.27	21.8	82274	1722.47
359	4780	1.73	139.47	21.8	82266	1722.97
360	4785	1.39	148.18	21.8	82272	1722.87
361	4790	2.22	143.86	21.7	82278	1722.87
362	4795	1.84	111.49	21.7	82269	1722.97
363	4800	2.01	103.58	21.7	82275	1723.46

[961 rows x 6 columns]

APPENDIX THIRTEEN

PHOTOGRAPHS

Figure 1: Lab Work

Figure 2: Field Test

Figure 3: Online Wind Data Results

My Supervisors and I